

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPACT OF SOCIO-LINGUISTIC AND SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS ON TRANSLATION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The article scrutinizes translation or interpretation process in terms of socio-linguistics and socio-cultural factors. As mentioned in the study technology also builds up a bridge between the translator and the speaker. The translator/interpreter should have some qualities such as professionalism, cognitive skills, language skills, ability of using cutting-edge technological devices. Moreover, the translator should own cultural awareness about both source language and the target language in order to translate or interpret the information properly. The translator should be knowledgeable about the information in advance. Apart from linguistic skills, a professional translator or interpreter should have supernatural skills such as the ability of approximating what could be told in advance.

Keywords: interpretation, translation, cognitive skills, socio-linguistic factor, cultural awareness.

INTRODUCTION

The professional people are prone to be obstinate in terms of personality showing a behavioral role model for others. In spite of contradictory opinions, everybody is treated equally and avoid segregation [2]. The major professional principles that the interpreters should follow are impartiality, planning, punctual delivery, patience, confidentiality and discipline. Furthermore, the interpreter or translator must be objective. So that he/she should be fair and free from personal views, beliefs, weakness and feelings. "He/she should be humble and willing to learn, develop, change, know himself/herself" [13, p.97].

Obviously, Nida showed that an interpreter or a translator owns a deeper comprehension of the bonds between their work and various human characters- one more time stressing a distinctive character needed for the profession. Perfectionism or completeness should be regarded as a form of professionalism. Interpreters/translators should be attentive and precise in their jobs focusing on acknowledging and details which are the most complicated elements behind perfection in the maintenance of comprehensibility.

They know that misuse or omission of a word, wrong sentence pattern, a punctuation mark used in a flat or semiotic meaning may influence the content and ongoing process. In this regard, an interpreter or a translator evaluates the situation and tries to avoid translation mistakes encountered in technical and ethical principles to gain a more comprehensively acceptable and professional version of the work which is in progress.

Moreover, Rudvin claims that "professionalism is far from being a universal corporate value, but rather a culture-bound social practice and that this culture boundedness affects interpreters' codes of ethics, their understanding of their own role, recruitment and quality factors and consequently their interpreting strategies" [14, p.49]. Rudvin's view is a reality. Since interpreters/translators determine common comprehensive standards for professionalism. They could underestimate the cost of such context. Hence, professionalism should be handled in translator's own socio-cultural at-

mosphere to provide them with the chance to better realize the ethical values and standards in a smaller community. Hence next professional purposes might be determined for a world market. For this reason, professionalism is associated with local requirements and reality in a particular profession.

Ethics are related to professionalism, too. They are interrelated, but not identical completely. First of all, an interpreter's ethical values are for himself/herself. Such values have the common beliefs and comprehension of the interpreter's family background and atmosphere surrounded with the pragmatic understanding of socio-cultural reality. The translator/interpreter, in this regard, should be personally ethically-oriented primarily. This notion shows itself in a broader sense because ethical values can't be universalizes and the concept of professionalism differs from subject to subject.

In the meanwhile, it is vital to mention the interpreter's/translator's socio-cultural schemata. From linguistic point of view, this schemata reflects his/her intercultural and communicative skills. Because they are in an ongoing attempt to develop their pragmatic skills under natural and conscientious conditions through taking on communicative and cultural experiences as parts of everyday life. Canale stressed the importance of socio-linguistic skill in her model of communicative competence. As to Canale "Socio-linguistic competence is concerned with human interaction in natural contexts; utterances, as they are produced and meant in various socio-cultural contexts. The socio-linguistic competence is quite important since it is genuine for real communication" [4, p.7].

The translator/interpreter must develop communicative skills, first of all, in native context and he/she should watch, stress and learn the ethics of life in natural context. Hence by means of effective communication skills, the ethics of professionalism would be improved via socio-cultural practice.

MAIN PART

Cognitive skills

Although interpretation has been explored from a number of perspectives, there is no doubt that achievement of cognitive skills and their representations in the interpretation/translation process is very crucial which is a cognitive and communicative activity went on textual operation. When we say a text, it does not mean that it is absolutely in written form. The material that we also call a text may be in spoken form as well. So, irrespective of the spoken and written form, the cognitive activity is in progress. Dechert and Sandrock carried out an empirical experiment on the psycho-cognitive aspects of interpretation/translation [6]. Similarly, Gerloff [9,p.135], Krings [11,p.263] and Lorscher [12,p.26] focused on how verbal process occurs during the interpretation/translation. Cognitive studies led to a better comprehension of creative and critical thinking, problem solution, strategy development, perception, acquisition and memory processing. A number of various cognitive skills or types of attention are enumerated below;

1. Attention: In spite of distractions from various sources, the skill to concentrate and maintain it
2. Sustained attention: Focusing on the assignment effectively for longer period of time even if there are other existing distracting factors.
3. Selective attention: The ability to deny inappropriate stimuli and increase the awareness on what should be done for a certain period of time.
4. Split attention: The ability to implement multi-tasking assignments. In this respect, a synchronous interpreter must be able to use her/his long-term and short-term memory simultaneously. In this regard, cognitive skills such as auditory intelligence, focus, speed, attention, visual intelligence and perception are used wholly. In the meanwhile cognitive load increases on the necessity to integrate the different sources of stimuli mentally.

The irrelevant cognitive load appears to have a negative influence on the mental integration of input data as translator/interpreter reads, listens, perceives, observes, evaluates and relates both the assignment in progress and ahead.

To be knowledgeable

Interpreters know about cultural, social, political, economic and scientific progress happening both at local and universal levels. They are active readers and know about the agenda that they follow, semantic and grammatical structures used there, the further tasks and language requirements. We may say that the interpreter's desire to read and supply himself/herself with current information turns into a way of life which can be given up. It is considered to be more than a personal hobby. In this respect, translator's or interpreter's mental activities should be taken into consideration. Gile is the first well-known linguist to introduce the thought of extra-linguistic knowledge in this profession. As to Gile, comprehension should be developed in order to process the outcomes of interpretation/translation assignment [10]. The relevant form of extra-linguistic input gained in the collection of data also identifies the quality of the work implemented. Such extra-linguistic

knowledge would include worldwide issues, socio-cultural practice, communicative practice in various target and local contexts, anthropological and humanistic disciplines, personal code of conduct and no doubt, willingness to move beyond one's comfort area for more experience, data processing, observation, functionality and thinking.

Mastery of grammar

Interpreter's knowledge of both native language and target language should be detailed and perfect. They should be able to express themselves in different social and professional platforms. Arslan said: "An individual who does not have any knowledge of language, even attempting to get into the translation process would be a wise one. He should be able to use both languages verbally and in writing, so that he can be in the field" [1]. Though this feature makes difference in interpretation/translation from practical and theoretical points of view, the diversity sources from the fact that they should be proficient listeners and readers irrespective of the subject. Eradam claims: "The person who will become a translator should be aware of semantics, sociolinguistics and stylistics and ought to be able to apply this information on the texts" [7, p.70]. Briefly saying, the interpreter is a facilitator that provides interdisciplinary interaction. They are those who view language professionally, they are aware how to employ various verbal and written styles, use them in their job.

To carry out communicative practice in different socio-cultural contexts more efficiently and effectively, formation of a relevant grammatical skill is one of the most essential requirements. It represents the theoretical-structural aspects of language. Grammatical competence is an ability to grasp and interpret the sense by means of production of syntactically and morphologically constructions. The formation of grammatical competence needs control over structured words, sentences and phrases. The ability to control linguistic structures during interpretation will end in more efficient communicative practice which will help the development of communicative skills, too.

Grammar rules implemented by the interpreter ought not to be regarded as the end, but ought to be a tool helping to effective interaction. There is not any time to focus on the grammar in the process of an interpretation assignment. Grammar knowledge allows relevant and strategic language use in specific communicative contexts as a computer system which operates in the background. In its turn, it helps the interpreter to focus on other functional aspects of work rather than grammatical constructions only. Babayev Javid underlines the significance of grammatical and lexical structures in translation process; "For a high quality translation, a translator should have a good memory(receptor) in order to receive and retain the information in mind respectively, a strong attention or focus on the grammatical and lexical structure of both languages, high language proficiency in native and target languages, fluency in speech and the ability to approximate what can be told next" [3, p. 118].

Cultural awareness

An interpreter is a professional person that must be able to balance social life and job. Simultaneous

translation is a problem in this meaning since interpreters work within geopolitical, social and economic momentum as the changing world forces them to go where they should without any hesitation. In this regard, interpreters are not just workers following some definite rules. Besides the native language, they should get acquainted with the customs and traditions of the target language knowing that a language is a cultural reflection and it is impossible to do proficient translation without perception, awareness and comprehension of cultural elements in both native and foreign languages. Therefore, the cultures of which they interpret from the people who form those customs and traditions and the Sapir Whorf hypothesis set forth in the middle of XX century on the way of thinking about people using language and style-all play an indispensable role in successful interpretation. Interpretation does not only affects the way we exchange the customs and traditions and knowledge among various communities, current universal conditions require that the interpreters take it one step further. For this reason, the formation of cultural competence emerged in social experience play a major role to carry out better. As to Choban, culture and subject area "Knowledge constitutes one of the basic elements of translation competence. A translator understands and creates a target text based upon previously obtained culture and subject area knowledge" [5, p.172]. So it is obvious that those who fail to improve a relevant cultural competence are also likely to fail in perception of the pragmatic comprehension of the spoken and written material.

Mey thinks that Linguistic behavior is social. People converse since they are eager to socialize in a broader sense of the word, either for entertainment to introduce themselves to other men or for some serious aims. Identification of the interpreter's linguistic behavior with social behavior demonstrates that proficient language knowledge is also consolidated by means of socio-cultural experience and gathering of such attempts are shown in the performance.

In any way, interpreter develops her/his pragmatic ability as her/his socio-cultural communication occurs in various contexts. Chin Lin adds: "learners can understand the meanings of language from a broader intercultural feature. As the students have a basic concept of pragmatic organization they will be more responsive to people's intended meanings implanted in worldwide communication" [5, p. 56]. In the meanwhile, like students, the interpreters' pragmatic ability assists them to obtain an outlook toward addressing their own professions in a broader sense.

In short, developing the cultural competence according to social experience assists the formation of pragmatic competence. This increases both the awareness of cross-cultural disciplines and gives a rise to the development of communicative skills as the attention changes from local to global views.

Being able to use modern technology

Interpreters should use technology and be in contact with other colleagues in the world as a consequence of the interpretation programs that they use. In the past nobody believed that such interrelation might be a real-

ity. Actually, they were right to think so, to some extent. However, lots of things have changed since 1940. Turker claims " Science has changed, technology has changed, people's value judgements have changed and above all computers have changed" [15, p.138]. In the mean, the interpreter should be an independent researcher. In some cases, some words which are difficult to find encourage further researches into various sources for hours, days, weeks even months and years. This attempt sharpens the interpreter's sense of systematic research as they delve into other related words. This quality sources from the attentiveness of their work and the comprehension of perfection. In this way, they achieve more discipline and be more target-oriented.

As the interpreter uses modern technology and carries out research, strategic and semiotic competences work simultaneously. Data evaluation, planning what should or have to be done, the way the interpreter reacts to a particular matter, creative and critical thinking for problem solution are possible with the development of strategic competence. Strategic competence is considered to be a meta-cognition of an interpreter's work. Similarly, meta-cognitive competence is also bred by semiotics since it deals with the ability to know the signs and symbols to interact data. Erton writes: "The semiotic capacity of an individual reflects the effective and efficient usage of pragmatic competence in which the language user has the awareness of socio-cultural and anthropological conventions processed and produced in the course of communication. Such a capacity also enables a systematic usage of cognitive skills, thereby developing the value of the communicative contexts and the individuals in various discourses" [8, p.266].

In the example shown above, it is necessary to stress that the semiotic and strategic competences function as operational means to link important knowledge, capabilities and skills for an effective performance. Since the interpreter uses information technology devices, carries out research on the internet. He/she uses practical conclusions of semiotics and logical thinking skills to save time, be more fluent and implement more simultaneous assignments.

Interpretation is a communication activity and in this regard, the principles of data processing in human interaction. It is a comprehension of an integration of psychological, biological and social sciences and their representations in communication experience. As the interpreter carries out research and makes use of information technology tools or translation means, the bio-semiotic atmosphere of human character determines the essence of their work and the quality of the product.

Fluent speech

Besides the skills shown above, an interpreter is a skilled speaker and interacts correctly and fluently in both the native and foreign languages. Undoubtedly, interpretation is an ability which requires more than linguistic-translation skills. It is important to elaborate the discourse and to possess pragmatics for successful simultaneous interpretation since the translator must be able to realize the impact of the information on the target audience, as well as the speaker intends to deliver

so as to generate an identical effect with interpretation during the process. To obtain it, it is essential for everyone to inherit the interpreted language, as well as its grammar, to focus and to own a potent memory and practical skills without being exhausted or bored for a long time. Obler carried out a research on the cognitive features of simultaneous translators and their language use during the interpretation. He analyzed the outcomes of his own research with those of similar researches and he revealed that cognitive features of a person who is busy with simultaneous interpretation were very diverse and skilled in comparison with those who deal with other forms of interpretation. With these peculiarities, simultaneous interpreters know how to affect and control the audience effectively.

Moreover, phonological and phonetic features of the language should be encompassed properly by the translator. The research of both sub-disciplines of structural linguistics supplies the translator with the chance to encompass a big deal of utterance in the communication activities and increase the awareness of the translator to acquire these fields to take fluent and relevant action.

Phonetics is concerned with the biological features of speech articulation. For example, the place of articulatory organs makes a major distinction in the physical production of sounds. Tone, juncture, intonation, stress as the key components covered in diction a considerable field to be concentrated on by the translators. In the meantime, acoustic features of speech sounds and their auditory perception are also explored in phonetics. The neuro-physiological status of sounds are also researched to comprehend the neurological features behind the perception and production of speech sounds. The translator, in this regard, should know about the fact that mastery in phonological and phonetic features of target and source languages will cause success in many cases as the translation is conducted. Thus, the following considerations must be taken into account:

- 1) The translator is understood by the audience well because her/his correct pronunciation makes the understanding easy for the audience.
- 2) The translator may differentiate target sounds easily since she/he acquired the physical features of sounds in the target contexts.
- 3) The translator can manage the speed and the clarity of her/his speech for the better understanding by the audience.
- 4) The exploration of tone, stress, juncture and intonation provide the translation with the chance to identify and stress definite features in the sentence of speech production so that the audience are able to differentiate more or less vital features or matters to focus on.
- 5) The translator's perception is developed in a way to acquire sounds and systems of sounds in TL free from dialect, accents and idiolects
- 6) The translator's knowledge of phonology and phonetics allow audience to control and stimulate them to follow the event carefully and willingly. So, the audience is not left alone and becomes an active part during the whole event.

Conclusion

Consequently, we can claim that a person who got training in interpretation and translation must add, improve and employ a lot of various skills. Furthermore, the interpreter should always remember that interpretation is a language-oriented action and requires the formation of interpretation competence. This competence represents approximately all aspects of multidisciplinary character of interpretation. Language competence allows well-structured sentences and phrases to form the basis of more meaningful communicative activity both in spoken and written forms. Well-structured communicative skills lead to the establishment of an efficient socio-cultural competence that assists the interpreter to comprehend the world free from native practice and norms. This will allow interpreter to research the physiological and psychological aspects of human character and to realize their reactions in the work process better.

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